

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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NURSE DRIVEN MOBILITY PROTOCOL

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Falls among older adult patients in the hospital setting are a critical issue. In the project hospital, the number of older adult patient falls increased over the last three years. Existing evidence shows that mobilization of patients prevents functional decline and muscle loss. One fall prevention strategy is to promote early mobilization. A nursing mobility protocol can assist nursing staff to implement early, and continuous mobility interventions based on the patients assessed functional status.

This performance improvement project included conducting surveys of registered nurses' and nursing aides' perceptions regarding fall prevention and promotion of early mobility. In collaboration with the hospital's education and physical therapy departments and current best practices, an early mobility protocol was adapted from the existing hospital protocol. Staff members were educated and trained on the protocol before implementation. Data analysis consisted of the evaluation of existing data and survey results before and after the implementation of the mobility protocol. The data were analyzed from the hospital's existing aggregated reports. The data included fall rates, the length of hospital stay, physical therapy referrals, and mobility activities.

Data collected and analyzed demonstrated a significant increase ($t(24.40) = -5.46$, $p < .001$) in patient mobility activities. There was one fall during the study period which may have been contributed to increased patient acuity and limited nursing aide staff. There were no falls with injury noted. Therefore, a mobility protocol has the potential to

improve patient outcomes by guiding nursing care and empowering nurses to assist with and direct patient mobility activities.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	viii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	ix
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	1
Purpose Statement.....	3
Supporting Framework	3
Decreasing Falls in Older Adult Patients on a Medical Surgical Unit Using the PDSA Quality Improvement Model	5
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	8
Overview.....	8
Fall Prevention Interventions.....	10
Early Mobilization.....	12
Barriers to Early Mobilization.....	14
Nurses' Perceptions	15
Summary.....	17
METHODS	18
Project Design.....	18
Plan-Do-Study-Act Model: Plan.....	18
Setting	18
Stakeholders.....	19
Participants.....	20
Ethical Considerations	21
Plan-Do-Study-Act Model: Do.....	21
Early Mobility Protocol	21
Education	22
Surveys.....	23
Data Collection	24

Plan-Do-Study-Act Model: Study	25
Data Analysis	25
Results.....	25
Patient Demographics	26
Fall and Fall Rate.....	26
Staff Survey Results-Demographics	27
Nurses' Perceptions About Patient Falls and Patient Mobility.....	27
Compliance With Mobility Protocol.....	31
 DISCUSSION	 33
Limitations	34
Recommendations and Clinical Implications	35
 CONCLUSION.....	 38
 REFERENCES	 39
 APPENDIX A: AVERAGE LENGTH OF STAY-RUN CHART	 50
 APPENDIX B: PHYSICAL THERAPY REFERRALS C - CHART	 51
 APPENDIX C: USC IRB APPROVAL LETTER	 52
 APPENDIX D: CSULB IRB ACKNOWLEDGEMENT LETTER.....	 53
 APPENDIX E: STAFF SURVEY CONSENT	 55
 APPENDIX F: STAFF SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE	 57
 APPENDIX G: EDUCATIONAL SESSION OBJECTIVES AND PLAN.....	 58
 APPENDIX H: EARLY MOBILITY DATA COLLECTION FORM.....	 59
 APPENDIX I: MOBILITY PROTOCOL TOOL	 60
 APPENDIX J: IN CONFERENCE POSTER ACCEPTANCE LETTER.....	 61
 APPENDIX K: TABLES OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL.....	 62

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Mobility	9
2. Nurse Perception.....	10
3. Fall Prevention.....	10
4. Demographics of the Nursing Staff.....	29
5. Nursing Staff Perceptions	30

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Quality improvement model: PDSA.....	5
2. PDSA framework to decrease falls in older adults with the use of a mobility protocol (adapted from Langley, 2009).	7
3. Fall rate of project unit: September 1, 2017 through January 4, 2019.	27
4. The mean of minutes up to chair.	31
5. Nursing compliance with mobility protocol.	32

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BACKGROUND

Falls among older adult (OA) patients in the hospital setting are one of the most critical issues in health care today (Centers for Disease control and Prevention [CDC], 2015). Falls among OA patients are concerning because they often lead to severe illness and in some cases death (Anderson, Postler & Dam, 2016). Fall prevention is a concern for hospitalized patients around the world (Barker et al., 2016). Over 150,000 falls lead to injury in the United States [Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI, 2018)]. It is essential to decrease falls among OA patients in the hospital setting to reduce mortality and morbidity rates, as one-third of OAs fall each year due to muscle weakness (IHI, 2018). The World Health Organization (2013) specified that, in the United States, 20% to 30% of OA falls result in moderate to severe injuries. One of the Joint Commission's Hospital National Patient Safety Goals (NPSG) for 2018 was to decrease falls since they account for a significant share of injuries among hospitalized patients.

Problem Statement

In 2016, The Joint Commission (TJC) reported an estimated 700,000 to 1,000,000 patient falls occurred that year in the United States. The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) have determined that falls in the hospital should never occur and stipulated that related expenses will not be reimbursed. Poor patient outcomes that occur due to falls add an average of 6.3 days to a patient's hospital stay and cost approximately \$14,500 per event (Haines et al., 2013; Wong et al., 2011). Poor patient outcomes include intracranial injuries, fractures, and death (Anderson et al., 2016). Dykes et al. (2010) report that a fall has the potential to decrease mobility and further places a

patient at a higher risk for falls. Patient falls are upsetting to the patient, and family, and may lead to litigation, resulting in increased health care costs (Sahota et al., 2014).

Since it is widely recognized that falls are an issue that demands attention, a variety of strategies have been examined to reduce fall statistics (Hempel et al., 2013). One of the strategies is early mobilization. Hospitalized patients who remain in bed for extended periods of time have a decrease in functional status and may be more likely to fall. Pashikanti and Von Ah (2012) indicate extended immobilization may decrease the functional status of a patient and increase the patient's risk of adverse outcomes for nurse sensitive clinical indicators such as falls. Furthermore, the lack of mobility in a patient admitted to the hospital can place the patient at risk for other health problems such as pneumonia, deep vein thrombosis, a decline of functional status with elderly patients are at higher risk for these morbidities (Liu et al., 2015; Teodoro et al., 2016).

Patients who remain immobilized during hospital stays lose muscle mass each day (Pashikanti & Von Ah, 2012). Fan et al. (2014) explained that with every day of immobilization due to bed rest, there is a 3% to 11% deterioration in muscle strength. Furthermore, a decrease in muscle strength leads to a decline in functional status. Fraser et al. (2015) describe higher mortality rates in patients who remained in bed and extended periods of immobility.

Recent research has examined a variety of early mobility interventions, programs, and protocols in the intensive care unit (ICU) setting that demonstrates prevention of functional deterioration and a decrease in hospital-related complications (Tipping et al., 2017; Barnes-Daly, Phillips & Ely, 2017). Nurse-driven mobility protocols increase the chance a patient will ambulate within the first three days of hospitalization in the ICU

and acute care setting (Drolet et al., 2013). While there is evidence of improved outcomes of early mobility in ICU patients (Smith et al., 2018), there is little research on implementation of an early mobility protocol for patients in medical-surgical units. It is important to direct some of the early mobilization protocols to this population.

This QI project took place at an academic level one-trauma center in Southern California, which has 600-beds, and cares for an underserved population. Difficulties in decreasing patients falls is not unique to this hospital as it is a national problem (Zhao et al., 2018). The project hospital has a fall rate among OA patients of 2.80 per 1000 patient days. The number of OA patients falls has increased over the years. In 2015, there were 55 falls, 2016: 90 falls, and 2017: 109 falls.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this DNP project was to implement an evidence-based mobility protocol on a medical-surgical unit at a hospital in Southern California with the aim of reducing the number of falls among OA patients. The following objective was carried out to identify and modify a mobility protocol appropriate for a medical-surgical unit.

Supporting Framework

The Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) Model supported this quality improvement project. According to Moen and Norman (2010), W. Edwards Deming developed the PDSA Model between the years of 1986 and 1993. The PDSA was first developed for business and continuous process improvement (Langley, 2009). The PDSA Model is widely accepted in healthcare, as it is a simple and effective approach to quality improvement (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], n.d.).

The PDSA Model consists of four stages: Plan, Do, Study, and Act. The four stages are considered a cycle (Deming, 1993). According to Crowl, Sharma, Sorge, and Sorensen (2015), PDSA cycles are meant to provide a quick method to guide change and determine if the change results in the desired outcome. If the intervention does not produce an expected outcome, then the intervention can be adapted or abandoned (Crowl et al., 2015). In the PDSA Model, failures are viewed as opportunities to gain knowledge and adapt or try another intervention (Langley, 2009). The implementation of a new or modified change designates the start of a new PDSA cycle.

The first stage entails planning the change; therefore, a team is formulated after a problem is identified (Langley, 2009). The team maps out the process and identify areas of vulnerability that may be causing the problem. The team brainstorms ideas for change or intervention, and all suggestions are considered. After brainstorming, the team determines which change will be tested and arrives at a consensus regarding the questions that need to be answered. The team hypothesizes answers to the questions, and then develops a plan for data collections (Langley, 2009). The next stage, Do, is where the change is implemented. Afterwards, outcomes and both planned and unplanned observations are recorded (Holly, 2014). During the Study stage, outcome and observation data are collected regarding the change implemented and compared to the hypothesis (Langley, 2009). In this stage, it is determined if the change produced an improvement (Langley, 2009). The last stage is Act, and it involves having the team evaluate the change and lessons learned (IHI, 2017). It is important that lessons learned are discussed to develop a plan to prevent drawbacks from being repeated. If the results are not favorable, an adjustment to the intervention can be made, or the idea can be

abandoned, and another intervention tested. This begins another cycle of the PDSA Model. If the quality improvement change is favorable, it can be refined, and implemented throughout the organization. The intervention is then evaluated for sustainability (IHI, 2017).

Figure 1. Quality improvement model: PDSA.

Decreasing Falls in Older Adult Patients on a Medical Surgical Unit Using the PDSA Quality Improvement Model

The PDSA model was appropriate to use for this QI project to decrease falls among OAs (Figure 2). The Plan stage included bringing a team of key stakeholders together to provide suggestions to change current practices to improve patient mobilization. The team consisted of frontline nursing staff, nurse managers, physical therapists, a quality improvement manager and the medical director. The team provided hypotheses to questions regarding the change and developed a plan to collect data. The Do stage included adapting and implementing a nurse mobility protocol at the project medical-surgical unit. The team recorded observations that were both planned and unplanned.

The purpose of this QI project was to develop and implement an early mobility protocol to reduce falls on a medical-surgical unit among OAs. The A-F ICU mobility protocol was tailored for the Medical Surgical unit. For example, awakening was not evaluated on the project unit since patients are usually not sedated. During the Study stage, the team examined nursing staff members' compliance with electronic medical record documentation, indicating patient mobilization, physical therapy referrals, and time between falls. The last stage was Act, which means the team evaluated if the change had positive outcomes and discussed lessons learned. Evaluation of the implementation of the mobility protocol was analyzed to determine if it had an effect on patient falls or fall rate, inpatient OA mobility activities, physical therapy referrals, or on length of stay. The team identified another unit on which the mobility protocol was tested and was implemented hospital wide.

Figure 2. PDSA framework to decrease falls in older adults with the use of a mobility protocol (adapted from Langley, 2009).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

An online literature search was completed using PubMed, Cumulative Index for Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), Google Scholar, Science Direct, One Search, Ovid, Sage, and EBSCO. The search terms used were early mobility programs, early mobility protocols, mobility bundles, early progressive mobility, barriers to early mobilization on medical-surgical units, hospital falls in older patients and hospital length of stay related to falls. The search included English language articles published after 2013, with the exception of one article that relates to early mobilization in the medical surgical setting, in scholarly online peer-reviewed journals. Additional sources that were the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, the Department of Health and Human Services, the Centers for Disease Control, the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services, The Joint Commission, the IHI, Institute of Medicine, and the National Centers for Biotechnology Information—National Institutes of Health.

A literature review was performed to appraise research regarding nurses' perception of their role in patient mobilization and fall prevention in the acute care hospital setting. Keywords used in the search were nurses' perceptions and beliefs related to patient mobility in the hospital setting and nurses' perceptions and beliefs related to fall prevention in acute care settings. Exclusion criteria for this literature review consisted of studies related to falls at home, home mobility programs, and publications that focus on the increased length of hospital stays that did not relate to inpatient falls. Exclusion criteria identified did not pertain to this project and had the potential to skew the data results.

The table of evidence includes the following subtopics: Fall Prevention Interventions, Early Mobility-Mobility Programs/Bundles/Protocols, Use of Early Mobility and Mobility in the Medical Surgical Units, and Nurses' Perceptions about Fall Prevention and Patient Mobility (Appendix K).

Table 1

Mobility

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Early mobility OR programs OR protocols OR bundles OR progressive mobility	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2013-2018	PubMed: 77 CINAHL: 819 GS: 11, 700 OS: 97,996	34 814 11,660 97,989	40 80 40 30	6 5 4 7
Barriers to early mobilization on medical-surgical units	Peer Reviewed, English language 2013-2018	PubMed: 17 CINAHL: 11 GS: 17,300 OS: 512	16 11 17,300 512	17 11 30 25	1 0 0 0
Hospital falls in older patients	Peer Reviewed, English language 2013-2018	PubMed: 622 CINAHL: 10 GS: 17,800 OS: 17,462	618 7 46 59	50 10 46 59	4 3 0 0
Hospital length of stay related to falls	Peer Reviewed, English language 2013-2018	PubMed: 114 CINAHL: 1 GS: 20,400 OS: 5,640 SD: 2477		50 1 47 34 27	2 1 0 0 0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title or abstract and significance to project topic.
CINAHL = Cumulative Index Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINALH); GS = Google Scholar;
OS = One Search includes Science direct, OVID, SAGE, and EBSCO)

Table 2

Nurse Perception

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Nurse perceptions AND beliefs related to patient mobility in the hospital setting	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2013-2018	PubMed: 1 CINAHL: 185 GS: 16,900 OS: 2165	0 10 16,898 2165	1 10 18 15	1 0 2 0
Nurse perceptions AND beliefs related to fall prevention in the acute setting	Peer Reviewed, English language, Published Date: 2013-2018	PubMed: 0 CINAHL: GS: 17,300 OS: 1391	0 24 14 19	0 25 15 20	0 1 1 1

Note. Articles excluded were based on title or abstract and significance to project topic.
CINAHL = Cumulative Index Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINALH); GS = Google Scholar;
OS = One Search (includes Science direct, OVID, SAGE, and EBSCO)

Table 3

Fall Prevention

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Fall Prevention Interventions	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2013-2018	PubMed: 84 CINAHL: 637 GS: 17,600 OS: 27,961	36 72 57 52	40 75 60 55	4 3 3 3

Note. Articles excluded were based on title or abstract and significance to project topic.
CINAHL = Cumulative Index Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINALH); GS = Google Scholar;
OS = One Search (includes Science direct, OVID, SAGE, and EBSCO)

Fall Prevention Interventions

Patient falls in the acute care hospital setting are a significant patient safety concern (Goldsack, Bergey, Mascioli, & Cunningham, 2015; Titler et al., 2016; The Joint Commission, 2016; Weil, 2015). Patient falls are the most often reported adverse events in the acute care hospital settings (Anderson, Postler & Dam 2016; Quigley & White, 2013). Healthy People 2020 lists fall prevention as a goal because patient falls often lead

to severe injuries and death. Of particular concern are falls among OAs within the hospital setting as this is a group with poorer outcomes post event (Brummel et al., 2015; Hartung & Lalonde, 2017; Pedersen et al., 2013). Hospitalized patients may be bedridden for extended periods of time, which causes deterioration in functional status and places the patient at higher risk for hospital-related complications such as falls (Dermody & Kovach, 2017; Pashikanti & Von Ah, 2012). Fall prevention efforts in hospitals is further complicated by patient-related factors associated with medical co-morbidities and age (The Joint Commission, 2015).

Current hospital fall prevention programs are multidimensional (Breimaier, Haldens, & Lohrmann, 2015; Titler et al., 2016; The Joint Commission, 2015; Walsh et al., 2018). Researchers describe a variety of fall prevention interventions. Interventions are directed to address the patients' individual needs related to physiological, behavioral, and environmental factors (Breimaier et al., 2015; Dykes et al., 2017; Goldsak et al., 2015; Hardin, Dienemann, Rudisill, & Mills, 2013; Ramesh, Irene, & Tzyy Ping 2017). The multifactorial fall prevention programs include fall risk assessments tools and interventions that visually identify patients as high risk for falls. In September 2015, The Joint Commission issued a Sentinel Event Alert 55 that acknowledged the difficulties in fall prevention in the acute care environment. Sentinel Event Alert 55 was issued to assist organizations to identify strategies to prevent falls (The Joint Commission, 2015). The alert described various fall prevention toolkits that had some success with in reducing falls events and fall rates.

Hempel et al. (2013) conducted a systematic review of fifty-nine studies to determine the application, elements, use of, and effectiveness of fall prevention

interventions in acute care hospitals in the United States. The interventions most used were a fall risk assessment, visual cues for patients and staff members, education, patient rounds, bed alarms, and evaluations after a fall (Hempel et al., 2013). Interventions were targeted approaches based on the patients' overall risk for a fall. The researchers suggested that successful interventions are dependent on an accurate fall assessment, which individualizes the interventions specific to the patient's needs. They also concluded that the complex, multi-component, and individualized interventions as elements make it difficult to identify which specific interventions reduce fall rates. Other studies also acknowledge the lack of clarity about the value of each part of the fall prevention protocols, such that it is unclear which intervention lowered fall rates (Breimaier et al., 2015; Hempel et al., 2013; Ramesh et al., 2017).

A gap identified in the studies reviewed are mobility interventions specifically for fall prevention. Tipping et al. (2017) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis that identified an increase in muscle strength and improved ambulation with patients who engaged in mobility activities. Early ambulation has been shown to decrease length of stay and improve functional status in OA patients (Adogwa et al. 2017; Azuh et al. 2016; Santos et al., 2017). The AHRQ asserts that patients should be required to walk to maintain their functional status and prevent muscle loss, which prevents complications of immobilization such as a fall. The next section of this review focuses on early mobilization studies.

Early Mobilization

Early mobility is defined differently within studies. For example, Donnellan, Sweetman, and Shelley (2013) defined early mobility as the patient engaged in active

movement during mechanical ventilation. Drolet et al. (2013) identified early mobility as occurring within the first 72 hours from admission. Tipping et al. (2017) included active and passive range of motion in bed, sitting, walking, and standing as early mobility.

The literature supports early mobility in the ICU as an intervention to generally improve patient outcomes (Anderson et al., 2016; Anderson & Mikkelsen, 2017; Azuh et al., 2016; Dermody & Kovach, 2017; Fraser et al., 2015). The World Health Organization's (2013) International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health model provides guidelines for the implementation of interventions (including early mobility) to improve ICU patients' physical impairments. One of the goals is to mobilize ICU patients earlier in their stay and before discharge.

In a bi-national, multi-center, prospective cohort study, early mobilization was related to improved muscle strength in mechanically ventilated patients. These patients, when discharged from the hospital, had improved survival rates at day 90 (Hodgson et al., 2015). Santos, Ricci, Paisani, and Chivegato (2017) conducted a systematic review of nine randomized control trials and concluded that early mobility decreased the LOS, increased functional status, and eliminated postoperative problems compared to no mobilization.

There is sufficient evidence that mobilization of patients in ICU is advantageous to prevent functional decline and muscle loss. OAs hospitalized in ICUs are particularly vulnerable to insufficient mobility because of existing comorbidities (Brummel et al., 2015; Hartung & Lalonde, 2017; Mauzur, Wilczynski, & Szewieczek, 2016; Teodoro et al., 2016). When transferred from the ICU to the medical-surgical inpatient setting, there is a tendency for a patient to have significant muscle weakness and a decline in functional

status (Tipping et al., 2017). Therefore, it is imperative to continue mobility interventions on the medical-surgical units. Research affirms that medical-surgical nurses do not promote mobility in the older adult population (Doherty-King, Yoon, Pecanac, Brown, & Mahoney, 2014; Dermody & Kovach, 2017; Pedersen et al., 2013). A mobility protocol can assist nursing staff to implement early and continuous mobility interventions (Balas et al., 2013a; Drolet et al., 2013; Messer, Comer, & Forst, 2015).

Barriers to Early Mobilization

There are a variety of barriers in implementing early mobility protocols. One of the barriers is nurses' lack of knowledge regarding adverse outcomes related to immobilization (Admi, Efrat, Baruch, & Zisberg, 2015), specifically patient falls (Donnellan et al., 2013). Other barriers identified include lack of time (Dermody & Kovach, 2017), increased patient assignment loads, and high patient acuity level (Sepulveda-Pacsi, Soderman, & Kertesz, 2016).

In a systematic review of 40 studies on barriers to early mobilization of ICU patients, Dubb et al. (2016) illustrated that early mobilization was safe. The researchers identified four categories of barriers: patient-related, for example, diagnosis; structural, (lack of a specific protocol or poor staffing); ICU culture, (nurses' attitudes about the need for patient mobilization); and process-related, which pertains to staff members' knowledge or lack of understanding of their role. Smith et al., (2018) also conducted a study whose results of early mobilization protocol revealed the minimal impact on patient safety.

In another systematic review, Costa et al. (2017) found similar barriers to those identified by Dubb and colleagues, except for ICU contextual barriers. The barriers were

multifaceted with patient-related factors being the number one reason for decreased early mobility. Costa et al., (2017) identified 70 strategies to overcome barriers. In an earlier study of three academic centers, Engel et al., (2013) identified the following barriers to early mobility: lack of leadership, lack of staff and equipment, lack of knowledge or training, lack of physical therapy referrals, over-sedation, delirium, hemodynamically sensitive to activity, and safety. It is clear that, in order to implement early mobility interventions, barriers need to be addressed in order to achieve better outcomes. The following section describes nurses' perceptions related to promoting early mobility and fall prevention intervention.

Nurses' Perceptions

Nurses' perceptions and attitudes about promotion of early mobility interventions may have a significant negative impact on the prevention of adverse patient outcomes (Engel et al., 2013; Jolley et al., 2014; Kneafsey, Clifford, & Greenfield, 2015). In a descriptive study by Dermody and Kovach (2017), nurses identified that they lacked the training to implement safe mobility protocols. This was one of the barriers to mobilization identified in the systematic reviews. Of explicit concern was the nurses' lack of knowledge of how to assess lower limb strength. Nurses perceived that muscle strength was to be evaluated by the physical therapist; and that this assessment was outside their scope of practice. The nurses also expressed that the physical therapist should be totally responsible for patient mobilization (Dermody & Kovach, 2017). Nurses perceived patients' acuity as too high for them to implement patient mobilization and they reported that they lacked the confidence to implement mobility interventions in a safe manner. The finding that nurses were reluctant to implement early mobility as it

placed the patient at higher risk for injury was also reported in other studies (Engel et al., 2013; Jolley et al., 2014). The nurses in the Dermody and Kovach study (2017) also perceived that patients did not want to participate in mobilization.

The studies on nurses' perceptions regarding fall risk and prevention mimic the barriers identified in the systematic reviews discussed in the prior section related to mobility. Barriers identified in the literature regarding nursing staff perception of fall risk and prevention of falls included patient status, physical environment, patient and staff education, inconsistent intervention implementation, and factors beyond the nurse's control (Gibson & Lloyd, 2018; Wilson et al., 2016). The barriers perceived outside of the nurses' control were leadership, patient acuities, and patient load which led nursing staff to feel helpless as patients continued to fall even after implementation of interventions (Gibson & Lloyd, 2018; Wilson et al., 2016).

Wilson et al. (2016) completed a study related to nurses' perceptions of implementing evidence-based fall prevention interventions and application approaches to promote these interventions. The evidenced-based fall prevention interventions included ambulation three to four times a day, gait and strength training, and range of motion to address mobility risk. Nurses perceived these fall interventions as general, and they did not consistently apply the interventions, nor did they perceive them as important. Nurses lacked focus on patient-specific reasons that placed a patient at risk for falls, specifically patient mobility of patients. However, post-implementation of an evidenced-based patient-specific risk factor intervention, nurses identified mobility as essential for fall prevention (Wilson et al., 2016). Nurses' perceptions about fall prevention interventions and patient mobility are essential to address as they may guide an approach to engage

nurses in the use of an early mobility protocol (Jolley, Regan-Baggs, Dickson, & Hough, 2014).

Summary

Regardless of the implementation of various interventions, programs, and protocols, patient falls continue to occur (AHRQ, n.d.). The research illustrates the importance of nurses' perceptions regarding barriers to the mobilization of patients, fall prevention, and fall prevention interventions (Kneafsey, Clifford, & Greenfield, 2015; Gibson & Lloyd, 2015). Having an understanding and removing potential barriers before implementation of a mobility protocol will be more likely to ensure success. The literature supports early patient mobilization as an intervention to promote positive patient outcomes. Fall interventions focus on preventing falls but do not concentrate on early mobilization to improve functional status to prevent falls. It is essential to address mobility in hospitalized OAs, as the literature described the increased vulnerabilities of this population (Kneafsey, Clifford, & Greenfield, 2015). The research demonstrated a gap in the literature regarding early mobilization in the medical-surgical setting. Therefore, an adaption of early mobility protocol to improve muscle strength and functional status may help decrease falls and have a positive impact on patient outcomes. An early mobility protocol is needed to address all patients admitted to the medical surgical unit as an intervention to decrease falls.

METHODS

The purpose of this quality improvement (QI) project was to evaluate the effectiveness of an early mobility protocol at a 32-bed medical-surgical unit. The project unit was located in a large academic teaching hospital in Southern California. The primary aim of the project was to evaluate the impact of early mobility on the fall rate of older adults. Secondary interests included the effect of early mobility on the length of stay (LOS), physical therapy (PT) referrals, and the nursing staff members' perceptions about fall prevention and promoting early mobility. The PDSA model guided the process for this QI project, and this section was organized accordingly.

Project Design

This QI project used a pre-post research design to collect and evaluate data on the metrics listed above. A QI approach was appropriate for this project as it aimed to improve patient mobility at one facility. The U.S. Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS) specified that a QI project is a formal process that uses proven methods to analyze a healthcare problem and develop interventions to improve patient care (CMS, 2017).

Plan-Do-Study-Act Model: Plan

Setting

The setting for this project was a 32-bed adult medical-surgical unit in a 600-bed public level-one trauma center located in Southern California. Common patient diagnoses seen on this unit are general medical-surgical acute illnesses such as cellulitis, cholecystitis, esophagitis and other various infections. Nursing care provided to patients on this unit varies in degrees of recovery from diagnostic, therapeutic, and surgical

interventions. The majority of the patients cared for in this facility (66.1 %) are Hispanic and are of lower socioeconomic status, as 65.5% are below 200% of the federal poverty level (Office of Statewide Health Planning and Development [OSHPD], 2015a, 2015b). Many patients are non-English speaking, and translation services are available to nursing staff members to facilitate communication. The project unit maintains a 95% occupancy rate with an average length of stay of 5.9 days (OSHPD, 2015a).

The patient-to-nurse ratio on the unit is five patients to one nurse. There are usually two nursing attendants scheduled to take vital signs and assist patients with activities of daily living. This is a busy fast-paced unit with approximately ten admissions and discharges daily. The project facility does not have a hospital-wide mobility protocol, although there is a specific mobility protocol for the ICU patient. Patient mobilization is considered an element of routine nursing care, but certain mobility activities are directed by specific physician orders. For example, an order may be written as “ambulate patient three times a day.” A nurse-driven mobility protocol will guide staff to promote mobility and help ensure that patients do not have prolonged periods of bedrest. Patient mobilization activities are part of the required documentation in this facility but are not documented consistently. The information that is supposed to be documented is functional status on admission, activity level (up to chair, ambulating, and the need for assistance). Reasons for inconsistent documentation are explored in the assessment of the nurses’ perceptions of the early mobility protocol.

Stakeholders

The stakeholders of this QI project were the frontline staff members and the nurse manager of the project unit, the chief nursing officer (CNO), the chief executive officer

(CEO), the inpatient medical director, and the physical therapy department educator. Stakeholders are of the utmost importance in the PDSA model. Stakeholders are involved from the beginning of the QI project through implementation and conclusion. The overall goal for this project was to improve patient outcomes related to decreasing falls of older adults in the inpatient acute care setting by increasing mobility.

Since the patients were the recipients of early mobility protocol interventions, it was essential that the patient be educated. Education on the benefits of early mobilization can provide an understanding of how mobility will improve health, decrease the chance of an adverse outcome, and may lead to the patient fully participating in mobility activities.

During the planning phase, the stakeholders, or their designees, and frontline staff members met to identify obstacles to implementing change, which, in this case, was an early mobility protocol. The team predicted outcomes and devised a plan to collect data and overcome identified barriers. The anticipated project team consisted of a clinical nursing director (R. Sandoval as project lead), a physical therapist, the nurse manager, two RNs, two nursing attendants assigned to the project unit, and a medical resident. The CNO and CEO of the project hospital had already expressed a vested interest in this QI project.

Participants

Older adult patients admitted to the unit during the project period were the recipients of the early mobility protocol. This constitutes a sample of convenience. An older adult was defined as a person at least 65 years old. Patients on the project unit who had a physician's bedrest order were excluded from the project. Other exclusions were

patients who had cognitive impairments, patients who were non-ambulatory, and patients who were medically unstable.

The nursing staff in the unit who were responsible for implementing the protocol were a nurse manager, two supervising staff nurses, 41 frontline registered nurses, and 16 nursing attendants. All staff members were educated on the protocol as described below. Physicians and physical therapists, who were part of the multidisciplinary team, were informed about the project start date.

Ethical Considerations

The committee members for QI project, the institutional review board (IRB) of California State University Long Beach and the IRB of the project unit's hospital reviewed this project to ensure it met the standards to maintain protection for participants. IRB approval was obtained from the project unit's hospital IRB committee and from California State University, Long Beach on August 1, 2018 and August 27, 2018, respectively.

Plan-Do-Study-Act Model: Do

Early Mobility Protocol

The medical-surgical early mobility protocol was adapted from the ICU early mobility protocol that was already in place. A functional assessment score drove the patient's mobility activities. The adapted early mobility protocol had four levels (Appendix F):

1. independent- the patient should be out of bed to the chair at least three times a day and freely ambulate

2. minimal assist- the patient gets up to chair or sits at the edge of bed at least three times a day during meals and ambulates in room and progresses to walking down hallway with assistance from a nursing attendant or RN
3. moderate assist- up sitting on the edge of bed, standing with NA or RN maximum assistances
4. complete assist- turned every two hours and passive or active range of motion three times a day
5. complete bedrest- per physician's orders

The CNO, the director of the nursing education department, a nurse trained in the ICU mobility protocol, the physical therapy department educator, and the medical director of the inpatient medical-surgical units reviewed the early mobility protocol. Also, the chair for the project unit's hospital nursing protocol committee appraised the adapted protocol.

Education

A 30-minute educational session was developed and provided to unit nursing and physical therapy department staff members to introduce the early mobility protocol (Appendix C). The team lead (Sandoval) and one of the PDSA team members conducted the educational session. Six educational sessions were scheduled to reach nursing staff on all rotation schedules of the project unit. Nurses who were not available to attend one of the six educational sessions had individual training on use of the mobility protocol by one of the members of the early mobility PDSA team.

Two content experts, a physical therapist and a nurse expert for the ICU mobility protocol that was adapted, reviewed the teaching materials. Education sessions included a

review of the functional status assessment, the adapted mobility protocol, and permissible mobility activities directly related to functional status. Also, a review of the project unit's electronic medical record functional assessment tool was demonstrated.

Surveys

Before the educational session, a meeting occurred with staff to request their participation in a voluntary anonymous survey related to fall prevention and early mobility perceptions (Appendix B). Nurse perception is a barrier to early mobility, according to the studies reviewed (Dermody & Kovach, 2017). As part of this project, nurses received the survey pre- and post-implementation to assess attitudes and subsequent potential changes about early mobility and fall prevention. The six-question staff survey was developed from the review of the literature to address potential barriers for this QI project. Nurse demographic information that was included was age, gender, highest level of education, years of service and title. The four perception questions were rated on a six-point Likert type scale where 1 indicated Strongly disagree and 6 indicated Strongly agree. Two questions were dichotomous with responses of yes or no.

The survey was administered to the nursing staff before the introduction of the early mobility protocol and then repeated three months after the protocol's implementation. The post-implementation survey included a question on ease of using the protocol. The survey was administered pre-implementation from August 28, 2018, through September 5, 2018. Two nurses who returned from leave were provided an opportunity to complete the survey and were presented the mobility educational session on September 7, 2018, and September 11, 2018. The post-implementation survey was administered January 10, 2019, through January 16, 2019. The surveys were administered

through internet-based software. The process for administering the survey for the nursing participants was as follows:

- The project lead provided directions and consent
- Staff received the consent form and an envelope
- Staff were asked not to write their names on the envelope
- Staff were asked to place the consent form in the envelope signed or not signed
- Staff were told that the team would leave the room for 15 minutes to allow staff to complete the survey
- All staff were invited to attend an educational session

Collected consent forms, surveys, and data were locked in a file in the author's office.

Data Collection

A data collection sheet provided data about mobility activity regarding patient position and whether the patient got up to sit in a chair or ambulated. Data for patient fall rates, number of falls and falls with injury, were collected. National Database of Nursing Quality Indicators (as cited in AHRQ, 2013) described a "fall as an unplanned descent to the floor with or without injury to the patient" and this project used that definition (p. 1). The patient's age was included in the reports. Information on LOS and referrals to PT was also collected. LOS was defined as beginning at the time the physician writes the order to admit a patient to the hospital and ending at the time the patient is discharged and leaves the unit. Referrals to PT include the number of referrals during the project period. Post-implementation nurse perceptions were compared to baseline perceptions.

After the project received approval from the project unit's IRB committee and California State University Long Beach, data collection started (Appendix C and D). Baseline data about patient falls, LOS, PT referrals, and mobility activities were collected and reviewed from reports obtained from the nursing quality department. Data did not contain patient identifiers (Appendix D). Reports for a 4-month period prior to implementation of the adapted early mobility protocol and a 4-month period post-implementation were collected. A data collection sheet is in Appendix H.

Plan-Do-Study-Act Model: Study

Data Analysis

Using computer software, descriptive statistics were used to summarize information about the nurses, patients and other variables in this project. Difference scores were obtained to compare pre- to post-implementation information related to fall rates, the number of falls with and without injury, LOS, and PT referrals for patients aged 65 and older. Survey responses pre- and post-intervention were entered into Microsoft Excel and then uploaded into Intellectus for analyses. A *t*-test was used to analyze the differences between the means of nurse perception survey responses and patient mobility activity pre- and post-intervention (Polit & Beck, 2017). Graphs were constructed to illustrate trends and variation in the following: LOS, PT referrals, fall rates, and adherence to the early mobility protocol.

Results

The results section describes the outcomes of this QI project, which was aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of an adapted early mobility protocol on falls in hospitalized older adults. The fall rate and the number of falls for patients who met criteria for

inclusion are presented. Nurses' perceptions of preventing falls and increasing patient mobility were also evaluated. Various data points were collected pre- and post-implementation of the mobility protocol. The findings were as follows:

Patient Demographics

The project unit admitted a total of 147 patients aged 65 and older during the project implementation time from September 4, 2018, through January 4, 2019. Patients 65 years or older represented 25% of the total admissions to the project unit. Of these patients, 39% were male and 61% were female. Average length of stay for the sample patient population pre-implementation was 9.28 compared to the post-implementation length of 9.27. The difference was minimal. PT referrals pre-implementation were not significantly different (37.25) from post-implementation (34.75).

Fall and Fall Rate

During the study phase of this QI project, there was one fall that met criteria and occurred within the project timeframe (Figure 3). The fall rates were 0.00 in September, 1.08 in October, 0.00 in November, and 0.00 in all of December and through January 4, 2019 (Figure 3). Pre-data only included patients that met criteria to match the same characteristics of post data.

Figure 3. Fall rate of project unit: September 1, 2017 through January 4, 2019.

Staff Survey Results-Demographics

Demographic data were analyzed using the descriptive Intellectus Statistic software. There was a total of 72 surveys completed by staff: 25 (34.72%) pre-intervention and 47 (65.28%) post-intervention. A greater number of staff members completed the post-intervention survey versus the pre-intervention one. There were 53 (73.61%) registered nurses and 19 (26.39%) nurse aides who filled out the survey. The largest group identified themselves as between 30 and 39 years of age ($n = 27$, 38%). There were 66 (91.67%) females and six (8.33%) males. Members of both groups, registered nurses and nurse aides, had worked in the field for 1 to 3 years ($n = 39$, 54%). The majority of the participants had either Associate of Science in Nursing ($n = 26$, 36%) or a Baccalaureate of Science in Nursing ($n = 24$, 33.33%). Pre-implementation and post-implementation survey frequencies and percentages are presented in Table 4.

Nurses' Perceptions About Patient Falls and Patient Mobility

A two-tailed independent samples *t*-test was conducted through the use of Intellectus Statistic software to assess whether the mean of nursing staff perceptions pre-implementation was significantly different from the mean post-implementation (see Table 5). The result of the two-tailed independent samples *t*-test for nurses' perception for the statement "I feel empowered to prevent a patient from falling" was not significant, $t(68) = 0.25, p = .80$. The outcomes for the statements "I have time in my shift to ambulate a patient," "Bedrest increases the chance a patient will fall," "I feel empowered to promote patient mobility," and "Mobility improves patient outcomes" were not significant. During pre-implementation, 23 (92.0%) staff members acknowledged they were able to identify a patient with lower limb weakness. Post-implementation, that number was 45 (95.7%).

Table 4

Demographics of the Nursing Staff

Variable	Pre-Implementation	Post-Implementation
Are you a		
RN	17 (68%)	36 (77%)
Nurse aide	8 (32%)	11 (23%)
Age		
20-29	2 (8%)	14 (30%)
30-39	11 (46%)	16 (35%)
40-49	5 (21%)	9 (20%)
60-69	3 (12%)	2 (4%)
50-59	3 (12%)	5 (11%)
Your Gender		
Female	24 (96%)	42 (89%)
Male	1 (4%)	5 (11%)
How many years have you been a RN or NA		
1-3 years	12 (48%)	27 (57%)
10 years	8 (32%)	13 (28%)
7-10 years	3 (12%)	2 (4%)
4-6 years	2 (8%)	5 (11%)
Highest level of education		
ASN	6 (24%)	20 (43%)
Graduate Degree	5 (20%)	2 (4%)
BSN	8 (32%)	16 (34%)
Certification	6 (24%)	9 (19%)

Note. N = 72

Table 5

Nursing Staff Perceptions

Variable	Pre		Post		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
I feel empowered to prevent a patient from falling	5.20	1.12	5.13	1.04	0.25	.803	0.06
I have time in my shift to ambulate a patient	3.72	1.43	3.74	1.44	0.05	.957	0.01
Bed rest increases the chance a patient will fall	4.44	1.29	4.28	1.26	0.50	.620	0.12
I feel empowered to promote patient mobility	5.13	0.73	4.87	0.88	1.21	.230	0.31
Mobility improves patient outcomes	5.64	0.57	5.30	0.73	2.00	.050	0.51

Note. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 68. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Post-implementation, staff members responded as follows. As response to “The mobility protocol was easy to implement,” 4 (8.51%) chose Strongly Agree, 25 (53.19%) chose Slightly Agree, 10 (21.28%) chose Agree, 4 (8.51%) chose Slightly Disagree, 2 (4.26%) chose Disagree, and 2 chose (4.26%) Strongly disagree. There was not a significant mean difference in RN (4.38) and nurse aide (4.64) responses to “The mobility protocol was easy to implement.”

A two-tailed independent samples *t*-test was conducted to determine if the mean for the number of minutes the patient was observed in a chair pre-implementation was significantly different from the number post-implementation. The outcome of the two-tailed independent samples *t*-test was significant, $t(24.40) = -5.46, p < .001$. This finding suggests the mean of minutes sitting up in a chair pre-implementation was significantly different from post-implementation (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The mean of minutes up to chair.

Compliance With Mobility Protocol

Compliance with the mobility protocol was monitored through the mobility report and direct observation. Compliance with the mobility protocol increased each month of the study duration. Monthly compliance was as follows: 54.6% in September, 61.4% in October, 74.2% in November, 88.8% in December, and 83.7% in January. The QI project ended on January 4, 2019. Therefore, the January data only included the first 4 days of the month. Figure 5 illustrates bi-weekly compliance with the mobility protocol.

Figure 5. Nursing compliance with mobility protocol.

DISCUSSION

Older adult falls in acute care hospital settings continue to persist and cause a high percentage of adverse patient outcomes (Titler et al., 2016). Research supports that mobility activities help decrease falls by maintaining functional status and that medical-surgical nursing staff does not encourage mobility (Tipping et al., 2017).

During the 4-month QI project implementation period, there was one fall without injury. The fall occurred on a day the project unit had a high patient acuity index, and nursing aides were not available to assist patients with mobility activities. The literature supports that patient falls happen when there is high patient acuity (Duffield et al., 2015). The average length of stay and PT referrals did not significantly differ pre-implementation from post-implementation, which may suggest that the mobility protocol may have helped decreased patient fall rates.

During the study phase, the project author identified that a nurse mobility protocol did increase patient mobility activities, specifically in terms of frequency of getting patients up onto a chair and time spent in a chair. The mean of minutes in a chair increased by 21.75, and the documented occurrence of activities increased from 24 to 2260. Furthermore, compliance with the nurse mobility protocol showed improvement month to month. Although the last 2 weeks of data showed a slight decrease to 83.7%, the difference was within normal variation and was not significant. The last nine data points showed a shift with an average of 83.7%. This indicated the process was stabilized with a percentage improvement change of 82.4%. Research suggests that medical-surgical nurses do not encourage mobility in the older adult population (Dermody &

Kovach, 2017). However, this QI project showed an increase in patient mobility onto a chair that may be attributed to the nursing mobility protocol.

There was no significant difference between pre-implementation nursing staff perceptions and knowledge of falls and patient mobility and post-implementation results. The nursing staff on the project unit had an overall score of 92% pre-implementation and 95.7% post-implementation on the statement “Are you able to identify a patient with lower limb weakness.” The literature does not support this finding. Dermody and Kovach (2017), conducted a study that showed nurses acknowledged that they lacked the knowledge to assess lower limb strength, which was a barrier to mobilization. Studies identified a barrier to implementing an early mobility protocol was the nurses’ lack of knowledge regarding adverse outcomes related to immobilization, mainly patient falls (Donnellan et al., 2013). The “Mobility improves patient outcomes” statement had 100% response ranging from slightly agree to strongly agree pre-implementation, and 83% from slightly agree to strongly agree post-implementation. A probable explanation may be the lower number of staff members who completed the pre-implementation survey as compared to the post-implementation survey. Response scores to both of these survey statements demonstrated that the project unit nursing staff members perceived themselves as knowing how to assess lower limb strength and understood that increased bed rest could lead to adverse outcomes. Knowledge was not a barrier as identified in the literature.

Limitations

A limitation was that the QI project was conducted on one 32-bed medical-surgical unit. This created a small sample size which did not allow for sufficient data to

be collected in order to find significance. Falls occurred infrequently before the start of the project, which also limited significant findings. The OA fall rate for the unit before the protocol was 0.33 , one OA fall, and after the protocol 0.27, one OA fall. The fall rate was calculated by devising the number of falls per patient days which accounts for the differences in rate. Small sample size may limit the generalizability of the results but as a pilot there was not a negative impact.

Unanticipated findings during the Study phase pertained to the electronic medical record. The author of this project intended to use all data in the mobility activity report. However, analysis of the report showed that nursing staff were documenting the physicians' orders and not the patients' mobility activities. Therefore, only instances of a patient moving to a chair, which were documented to indicate the amount of time the patient was in the chair was used for this QI project. Another issue that was identified was reconciliation of the physicians' activity order upon transfer from an ICU to the project unit. Activity orders that were not reconciled correctly produced multiple activity orders for each patient transferred from the ICU. The multiple orders created confusion for the nurses. Ultimately, this lead to increased communication between physicians and nurses to clarify orders upon admission.

Recommendations and Clinical Implications

This QI projected provided an opportunity to evaluate the effects of a nurse mobility protocol on current patient mobility activities as these relate to decreased falls in OA. A mobility protocol provided guidance to nursing staff and, thus, increased patient mobility that may have decreased the fall rate on the project unit. This can be considered

a successful implementation. Therefore, in the act phase, the dissemination of the QI project to all other medical-surgical units in the project facility was initiated.

The recommendations for future PDSA cycles are to add a mobility protocol and increase understanding of how mobility activity is defined during new-hire orientation, how to document mobility requirements in the EMR, and rephrase the title header on the mobility activity section in the EMR. Mobility education included in new-hire orientation will help new nurses understand the importance of integrating mobility into their daily routine. There are many different areas to document and monitor in the nursing section of the EMR. The phrasing used in the mobility activity section of the EMR should be standardized and defined since currently nurses apply their own interpretation of what constitutes mobility. Standardization may lead to better documentation of patient activity levels.

A frontline ad hoc committee along with the EMR nursing documentation committee should review verbiage of the EMR mobility documentation modules. Also, an effort to streamline the mobility documentation sections should be part of the committee's objective. Frontline staff can provide the best perspective on how and why they document as they do. Frontline staff can provide suggestions on how documentation can be improved, which may lead to increased compliance with documentation. The concern of multiple patient activity orders was discussed with the project hospital's associate medical director for medical-surgical inpatient services. This was a system issue that required the assistance of leadership to help change. This issue has been forwarded to the enterprise EMR committee. A recommendation to include patient activity status on physician hand-off was made to the medical director. Should the above-mentioned

recommendations be implemented the hospital may see additional improvements in patient care outcomes. Future studies should be directed to assess data collection tools to determine if they capture information as intended, the impact of a high patient acuity index on patient mobility activities, and the nurse aide's role in a mobility protocol.

CONCLUSION

The nurse mobility protocol drove improvements in nursing care based on evidence-based practice. This QI project reminded the nursing staff about their role in patient mobility. Second, it provided the nursing staff with directions to encourage and promote patient mobility. This was important for several reasons. One reason was patients who had ad lib activity orders would stay in bed, and nursing staff did not address the patient remaining in bed prior to the mobility protocol. The effect of the mobility protocol was that patient mobility and functional status are now part of shift huddles organically brought forth by the frontline staff. Patients at risk for falls were already a part of the project unit's shift huddle discussion. According to the frontline staff on the PDSA team, the mobility protocol increased communication with physicians and physical therapists regarding patient mobility, clarification of activity orders, and empowered the nurses to make suggestion to increase patient activity status.

The implementation of a mobility protocol has the potential to increase the frequency and time an OA patient is out of bed during their hospital stay and, therefore, promote functional status to decrease the chance the patient may fall. Further improvement to the mobility protocol could be made once EMR committees address needed changes which could lead to further improvements in fall prevention.

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APPENDIX A
AVERAGE LENGTH OF STAY-RUN CHART

APPENDIX B

PHYSICAL THERAPY REFERRALS C - CHART

APPENDIX C

USC IRB APPROVAL LETTER

Rebecca Sandoval

From: istar-DoNotReply@usc.edu
Sent: Tuesday, August 07, 2018 12:12 PM
To: Rebecca Sandoval
Subject: Study Approval Notice Sent

Proposal #HS-18-00585

University of Southern California Institutional Review Board
 1640 Marengo Street, Suite 700
 Los Angeles, California 90033-9269
 Telephone: (323) 442-0114
 Fax: (323) 224-8389
 Email: irb@usc.edu

Date: Aug 07, 2018, 12:11pm
To: [Rebecca Sandoval, RN, MSN, MBA](#)
 Interim Clinical Nursing Director
 LAC + USC Medical Center

From: University of Southern California Institutional Review Board

TITLE OF PROPOSAL:

Implementation of a Mobility Protocol on a Medical-Surgical Unit: A Quality Improvement Project on a Medical Surgical Unit: A Quality Improvement Project ([Mobility Protocol](#))

Action Date: 8/7/2018 **Action Taken:** Approve
Committee: Institutional Review Board
Note: Your iStar application and attachments were reviewed by the IRB on 8/7/2018.

The project was APPROVED.

The materials submitted and considered for review of this project included:

1. iSTAR application HS-18-00585
2. Data Collection form
3. Mobility Methods 7-31-18
4. Consent Form
5. Timeline

APPENDIX D**CSULB IRB ACKNOWLEDGEMENT LETTER****CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS**

DATE:

TO: FROM:

PROJECT TITLE: REFERENCE #: SUBMISSION TYPE: REVIEW TYPE:

ACTION: EFFECTIVE DATE:

August 27, 2018

Rebecca Sandoval, MSN, MBA CSULB IRB

[1310789-1] Implementation of a Mobility Protocol on a Medical-Surgical Unit 19-043
New Project
Administrative Review

ACKNOWLEDGED August 27, 2018

Thank you for submitting the New Project materials for this Quality Assurance/Quality Improvement project. The California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board has ACKNOWLEDGED your submission. No further action on submission 1310789-1 is required at this time.

This is to acknowledge that the following documents are received:

- USCIRBProtocolApplicationHS-18-00585
- USCIRBReviewOutcomeLetter
- ApprovedInformConsentForm

Your project is considered Exempt according to the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services regulation at 45 CFR 46.101(b)(2) and therefore will not expire under the condition that the project continues to abide by University Policy regarding with Human subjects:

1. If you need to make changes/revisions to this approved project, you must submit a Request for Amendment to an Approved Protocol in addition to any documents affected by the requested change. Submit these documents as a subsequent package to your approved project via IRBNet. The CSULB IRB must approve the requested changes prior to implementing the changes to your project.

2. You are required to inform the Director of Research Integrity and Compliance, Office of Research & Sponsored Programs, via email ORSPCompliance@csulb.edu within twenty-four hours of any adverse event in the conduct of research involving human subjects. The report shall include the nature of the adverse event, the names of the persons affected, the extent of the injury or breach of security, if any, and any other information material to the situation.

3. Maintain your research records as detailed in the protocol.

- 1 - Generated on IRBNet

4. Respond to the Annual Check-In notice via IRBNet if you intend to continue the project after August, 26, 2019.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board's records.

1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840 Ph. (562) 985-8147 Fax.
(562) 985-8665

APPENDIX E

STAFF SURVEY CONSENT

Study Title: Implementation of a Mobility Protocol on a Medical-Surgical Unit: A Quality Improvement Project on a Medical Surgical Unit

Principal Investigator: Rebecca Sandoval

We invite you to take part in a survey that is part of a Doctorate in Nursing Practice Project. Please take as much time as you need to read the consent form. If you find any of the language difficult to understand, please ask questions. If you decide to participate, you will be asked to sign this form.

WHY IS THIS STUDY BEING DONE?

1. You are being asked conducted to increase the understanding of nursing staffs' perceptions and attitudes about fall prevention and patient mobility. We hope to learn how nursing staff feel about their participation in fall prevention and patient mobility. You are invited as a possible participant because you are part of the nursing staff on C6B. About 75 participants will take part in the survey.

WHAT IS INVOLVED IN THE STUDY?

1. The purpose of the quality improvement project is to implement and evaluate an evidence-based mobility protocol on a medical-surgical unit with the aim of reducing the number of falls among old adults. The survey you are being asked to participate in is to help understand the perceptions and attitudes of nursing staff regarding patient mobility and fall prevention. If you decide to participate you will be asked to complete an eleven-question survey on Survey Monkey. The total time of your participation is expected to last approximately 20 minutes. The survey results will be anonymous and will not be link to you. Signed consent will be kept in an envelope in a locked drawer in a locked office. You may directly benefit for participating in this study by becoming more aware of your perceptions and attitude toward patient mobility and fall prevention.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS?

1. Some of the questions may make you feel uneasy. You can choose to skip or stop answering any questions that make you uncomfortable.
2. There is a small risk that people who are not connected with this study will learn your identity or your personal information.

WILL YOUR INFORMATION BE KEPT PRIVATE?

1. *Consents will be locked in the quality improvement lead's office. Surveys will be completed through Survey Monkey. Survey results are not tied to each participants name.*

2. *Survey results are for a Doctorate of Nursing Practice Project.*

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE BENEFITS OF TAKING PART IN THIS STUDY?

You may not receive any direct benefit from taking part in this study. However, your participation in this study may help us learn if nurses' perceptions and attitudes help decrease patient falls and improve patient mobility.

WHAT OTHER OPTIONS ARE THERE?

1. *You do not participate in the survey.*
2. *Consents will be locked in a cabinet in an office of the lead for the quality improvement project.*
3. *There are no costs related to participation.*

WHAT ARE YOUR RIGHTS AS A PARTICIPANT, AND WHAT WILL HAPPEN IF YOU DECIDE NOT TO PARTICIPATE?

Your participation in this study is voluntary. Your decision whether or not to take part will not affect your current or future care at this institution. You are not giving up any legal claims or rights. If you do decide to take part in this survey, you are free to change your mind and stop being in the study at any time. You will not lose any rights if you decide to stop taking the survey

WHOM DO YOU CALL IF YOU HAVE QUESTIONS OR CONCERNS

You may contact Rebecca Sandoval at (323) 409-8841 with any questions, concerns, or complaints about the quality improvement project or your participation in this survey. If you have questions, concerns, or complaints about the quality improvement project and are unable to contact Rebecca Sandoval, contact the Institutional Review Board (IRB) Office at 323-442-0114 between the hours of 8:00 AM and 4:00 PM, Monday to Friday. (Fax: 323-224-8389 or email at irb@usc.edu).

If you have any questions about your rights as a quality improvement participant or want to talk to someone independent of the research team, you may contact the Institutional Review Board Office at the numbers above or write to the Institutional Review Board at 1640 Marengo Street, Suite 700, Los Angeles, CA 90033.

AGREEMENT:

I have read (or someone has read to me) the information provided above. I have been given a chance to ask questions. All my questions have been answered. By signing this form, I am agreeing to take part in this study.

Name of Participant

Signature

Date Signed
(and Time*)

APPENDIX F
STAFF SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

1. Are you a: RN _____ NA _____
2. Year of birth _____
3. Male _____ Female _____ Prefer not to state _____
4. How many years have you been a RN or NA? 1 -3 _____ 4-6 _____ 7-10 _____ >10 _____
5. Highest level of education: Certification _____ ASN _____ BSN _____ MSN _____
6. Are you able to identify a patient with lower limb weakness? Yes _____ No _____
7. I feel empowered to prevent a patient from falling? Yes _____ No _____
8. I have time in my shift to ambulate a patient?

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5	6

9. Bed rest increases the chance a patient will fall?

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5	6

10. I feel empowered to promote patient mobility?

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5	6

11. Mobility improves patient outcomes?

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5	6

Thank you for participating in this survey

APPENDIX G

EDUCATIONAL SESSION OBJECTIVES AND PLAN

Educational Session Objectives

1. Participant will be able to state two adverse effects of extended bed rest.
2. Participant will be able identify mobility activities for each functional status level.
3. Participant will be able to state two reasons when the mobility protocol would not be implemented.

Education Plan

1. Discuss decrease functional status and muscle loss with extended bed rest
2. Discuss adverse outcomes of extended bed rest
3. Safe Body Mechanics and patient mobility activities
4. EMR functional tool
5. Introduce the adapted early mobility tool and mobility activities
 - a. Independent
 - b. Minimal assistance
 - c. Moderate assistance
 - d. Complete assistance
 - e. Other
6. Allow time for questions

APPENDIX I

MOBILITY PROTOCOL TOOL

Mobility Protocol Tool

Note. Adapted from LAC+USC Medical Center's Functional Assessment-ADL Evaluation (2013), ICU Mobility Protocol (2015), and the Banner Mobility Assessment Tool for Nurses (2012).

APPENDIX J**IN CONFERENCE POSTER ACCEPTANCE LETTER****INSTITUTE OF NURSING'S 52ND ANNUAL COMMUNICATION
NURSING RESEARCH CONFERENCE**

Dear Rebecca Sandoval,

Congratulations ! Your abstract, "Implementation of a Mobility Protocol on a Medical-Surgical Unit," has been accepted for a poster presentation at the Western Institute of Nursing's 52nd Annual Communicating Nursing Research Conference to be held April 10-13, 2019 at the Town and Country Hotel and Convention Center in San Diego. Please notify any additional authors on your paper of this good news.

Your poster session is scheduled for Thursday, April 11, 2019 from 1:00 PM - 5:00 PM.

Conference registration is available [here](#) and a room at the Town and Country Hotel may be reserved [here](#). The conference program will be posted on the WIN website in the upcoming weeks.

Poster presentations are less formal, but not less rigorous or substantive, than podium presentations. Poster authors present their work interactively to groups of interested individuals with the aid of a visual display that summarizes research findings or project outcomes. Posters are displayed in a central location for four-hour blocks of time, so attendees can peruse the visual displays and talk with the authors. The WIN Program Committee has set aside one hour of time during each poster session in which the only scheduled activity is poster viewing. We ask that presenters stand by their posters during this hour, which will be listed in the conference program. **Poster boards are 4' x 8'**. Please visit the [Presenter's Corner](#) on the WIN website for valuable tips on presenting your poster.

As the Presenting Author, we ask that you log into the Presenter Information Center (link is below) to give your consent to present (see the "Consent to Participate" module) by Friday, January 4. Poster presenters do not need to upload presentation files, so please disregard that module in the Presenter Information Center.

We look forward to an excellent conference and to your participation. If you have questions, please contact Bo Perry by email at perrybo@ohsu.edu.

Sincerely,

Katreena Collette Merrill, RN, PhD
Chair, WIN Program Committee

APPENDIX K

TABLES OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Table 1

Interventions to Prevent Patient Falls

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures & Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
Evaluate the impact of pt. specific fall interventions (TRFFPB) (Titler et al. 2016)	Quantitative Prospective pre-post program implementation cohort study; Participatory partnership- QI project DV: fall rates, fall injury, types of injuries, no. and type of risk-specific interventions IV: TRFFPB compared pre-post implementation	13 adults m.s. units in 3 hospitals in US Midwest region Convenience sample, randomized Abstract of medical-surgical patients' charts, Pts. age ≥ 21 with a LOS > 24 hrs. (n = 390), Mean age of pt. 65.6 with 68% moderate or higher acuity	Medical record audits to evaluate the use of TRFFPB No. of falls with and without injury and type were aggregated Definitions: Fall, “an unplanned descent to the floor” and fall computations were completed as follows, incidents were “multiply by1000 and divided by patient days” (Titler et al. 2016, p. 55).	Multivariate analysis- Poisson regression model Fall rates: No statistically significant difference Pre: (fall rate 3.69) to post (mean fall rate = 2.7) Clinically significant 22% decline in fall rate Decrease in the severity of fall injury from major & moderate to minor Pre-26% post-11%	Limitations: Only involved acute care inpatient adult unit Conclusion the no. of falls with and without injury decreased with patient-specific fall prevention interventions. Increase risk of falling with aging, DNP project: TRFFPB EB fall prevention decreased the no. of falls. Mobility was one of the targeted fall prevention interventions in TRFFPB

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures & Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
Evaluate the effect of bed and chair alarms on elderly in-pt. falls (Sahota et al. 2014).	Quantitative, randomized controlled trial; Pragmatic, parallel-arm. IV: bed and chair pressure sensors DV: falls with and without injury.	UK hospital, three geriatric medical acute care units. Randomized convenience sample for the use of sensors was selected by a web-based service: Acute pts. aged 61 to 103 years of age (n = 1839).	Incident reporting form, Barthel ADL Index, MFES, LOS, dc location, quality of life questionnaire. Control group had sensors on their bed and bedside chairs linked to radio pager held by the nurse. Alarms when pt. stood up from bed or chair > 5 seconds. Equipment checked daily Fall per researchers: “unexpected event in which the pt. came to rest on the around, floor or lower level in the area around the bedside”. Fall with injury: “abrasion, bruise, swelling, cut, laceration, dislocation, fracture, or muscle sprain or strain”.	No statistically significant difference between study and control units for first time fall, incident reporting forms, Barthel ADL Index, MFES, LOS, dc location, quality of life questionnaire. Median LOS with falls 20 days vs. no falls 9 days. Fall rates: no statistical significance between intervention group 8.71/1000 bed days & control group 9.84/1000 bed days.	Pressure sensors using radio-pagers did not decrease the rate fall rate and are not cost effective for this population. Researchers indicate powered to detect 35% reduction rates based on pilot may be r/t with less decrease in bs falls that may have been missed. Potential under reporting of incident reports and inability to blind nursing staff to study. DNP project: This intervention does not decrease fall rates.

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures & Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
Comparison of fall occurrences in sr versus m-bws (Singh, Okeke and Edwards 2015)	Quantitative observational retrospective comparative- study Retrospective fall data on DATIX Variables: sr, m-bws, incidence of falls, falls with injury, mortality	General hospital in UK 18 mo. old site- m-bws and 18 mo. new site 100% sr Acute and sub-acute pts. age 70 to 90 admitted during study period Convenience sample No. of falls N = 1618	Fall data collected for 18 mos. from two hospital sites with M-bws (5/10 to 1/11) that move into one replacement hospital with sr. (11/11 to 12/14). Data compared before and after move for prevalence of falls with and without injury recorded on DATIX, LOS and mortality V&R not discussed Definition of fall not included	Falls/1000 pt. days: m-bws: 5.51 and sr: 15.83, statistically significant 2.9-fold > falls in sr Hip fx: m-bws: 0.04 ± 0.38 and sr: 0.15 ± 1.0 statistically significant LOS: m-bws: 44± 38 and sr: 34 ± 38 statistically significant Mortality rate: no statistically significant difference m-bws: 41.1% & sr 47.1%	More cases of falls with & without injury in sr More studies needed to examine sr impact on falls Limitations: Demographics did not include comorbidities. Confounding variables such as comparison to evaluate outcomes of those who did not fall- age, demographics, reason for admission were not controlled DNP Project: Assess if pts. who fall are in sr or double rooms. Explore recommendation for pt. placement in double room as an intervention for pt. at high risk for fall

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures & Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
Evaluate the impact of a FPTK using HIT on pt. falls in hospitals (Dykes et al. 2010).	<p>Quantitative cluster randomized study.</p> <p>Randomized interventions at the unit level</p> <p>IV: FPTK with use of HIT. EB fall risk assessment completed in HIT. HIT printed fall risk sign, pt. education pamphlet, POC, HIT alerts to the multidisciplinary team caring for the pt.</p> <p>DV: Falls with and without injury</p>	<p>Eight short-stay units in four US Boston, MA. Hospitals.</p> <p>Convenience sample of: all patients admitted to these units during study period (n = 10264 and 48250 patient-days).</p>	<p>Event reporting system to report falls with and without injury. Fall occurrences validated by NM.</p> <p>Variables studied and matched for historical data on fall rates and patient days</p> <p>Definition of fall: “Unplanned descent to the floor during the course of their hospital al stays” (Dykes et al. 2010).</p>	<p>No. of falls reduced in intervention versus control units.</p> <p>Adjusted fall rates were statistically significant: Study unit = 3.15/1000 pt. days. Control units = 4.18/1000 pt. days.</p> <p>No statistically significant difference for characteristics, fall risk scores, or falls with injuries.</p>	<p>HIT strategies that focus on principal areas of risk can prevent falls in older pts.</p> <p>The four hospitals were from one healthcare system with one fall risk assessment tool. Intervention not blinded. FPTK more effective in decreasing falls with pts. ≥ 65 yo) than in younger pts.</p> <p>DNP project: Assess age of pts. who experienced falls and explore recommendation to revise current HIT being used.</p>

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures & Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
Evaluate the impact of Webcams on falls and the MRA in identifying patients at risk for falls in medical surgical units (Hardin et al. 2013)	Quantitative Study-case control, descriptive design Hospitals and medical surgical units were randomly assigned to the intervention unit or control unit DV: Fall rate IV: Webcams with a central station for viewing the patients, “virtual bed alarm” for pt. with MRA>25	10 hospitals in the US from a health system that were identified as pt. falls > the benchmark 2.7 falls per 1000 pt. days Convenience sample pts. > 18 yo, had capacity, and admitted to the study unit	Fall rate per 1000 pt. days and fall rate per 1000 admissions Morse tool as an indicator for falls Focus groups- perceptions of Webcams Used NDNQI’s fall definition- “an unplanned descent to the floor with or without injury to the patient and occurs on an eligible reporting nursing unit.	Fall rates per 1000 pt. days: no statistically significant difference Fall rare per 1000 admissions: statistically significant difference Clinically significant- iu had less falls and less fall with serious injuries MRA significant predictor of fall risk- increase no. of falls with score ≥ 50 MRA Focus group- Webcam beneficial for geriatric pts. with dementia or delirium, post-op pts. And pts. With mobility limitations	Decrease in falls Webcam and increased awareness of fall prevention MRA identified pts. At high risk for falls Web cam scan improve observation of pts. without limiting mobility Limitations: decrease no. consent rates at intervention hospitals, selection bias, general applicability of the findings DNP Project: Webcam can be used without limit mobility. Falls generate guilt and decrease job satisfaction for nurses

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures & Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
Evaluate the impact of pt. centered hourly rounds on pt. falls (Goldsack et al., 2015)	<p>30-day prospective pilot study use Lean Six Sigma</p> <p>PI project with pre-post evaluation</p> <p>Variables: Fall rates, 1st unit staff involved with IP from implementation period, 2nd unit staff involved for training just before the implementation of hourly rounding</p>	<p>Two medical units at 907 bed academic hospital in Newark, Del.</p> <p>Convenience sample</p> <p>1st unit-35-bed medical stroke unit</p> <p>2nd unit-40 bed hem/onc unit</p>	<p>Staff survey, fall rates- fall per 1000 pt. days, compliance with hourly round process</p> <p>No fall definition</p>	<p>1st unit- 1-year baseline statistically significant fall rate decreased from 3.9/1000 pt. days to 1.3 falls/1000 pt. days</p> <p>2nd unit no statistically significant difference</p> <p>1st unit- positive perceptions of hourly round and viewed as a means to decrease workload</p> <p>2nd unit perception PI did not have a positive impact on pt. care and overall did not perceive this PI project as decreasing their workload</p> <p>Both units showed process compliance</p>	<p>Staff and leadership involvement from the beginning of the PI project- hourly rounds decreased fall rate and call lights in a medical unit</p> <p>Staff members perception was a factor in decreasing falls</p> <p>Limitation: short pilot study period</p> <p>DNP Project: Staff members perceptions are important when implementing a change</p>

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures & Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
Evaluate the effectiveness of a multifactorial and pt. specific interventions in implementing an EB fall-CPG prevention-guide into practice. And 2 nd aim evaluate cost benefit to implement the CPG(Breimaier, Halfens and Lohrmann 2015)	Qualitative and Quantitative Mixed-method design used within a participatory action research (PAR) approach, before-and-after Variables: nurse knowledge, cost-benefit,	Two departments in an acute care hospital teaching hospital in Austria Purposive sample: All graduate and assistant nurses	Questionnaires, group discussions, and semi-structured interviews Data collected at 3 points in the study (t1 = baseline, t2 = mid-term, t3 = end) Questions based on CFIR Define Effective implementation: “as an increase in the nursing personnel’s knowledge about fall-prevention measures; a positive change in their attitude towards evidence-based guidelines and the fulfillment of successful implementation criteria.” Qualitative—content—analyzed with CFIR	Statistically significant were Knowledge gained on fall prevention, about the CPG & where to locate the guideline Nurse perceived their increased awareness of fall prevention as most important part of project, nurses exhibited positive attitudes in regards the guidelines Implementation was timely and costly 150 personnel invested about 1192 hrs.	Limitations: Unable to determine before and after changes- unable to ID participant at t2 and t3, < 20% could remember their identifier, delay competing project, staff on vacation, additional units were added to study Conclusion: Multifaceted approaches specific to implementation using a PAR approach and directed by a CRIF were efficient in implementing CPG DNP Project: * Also, addressed attitudes and perceptions

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures & Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
			Quantitative data— descriptively analyzed		
			1 st invest. Responsible for all meetings with staff, Head nurse responsible for recording sessions & time keeping & education sessions		
Examine elements to fall prevention in the US(Hempel et al. 2013)	Systematic review Studies reporting in- hospital falls Inclusion Criteria: Participants: studies evaluating fall prevention interventions in hospitalized pt. Interventions: focused on reducing falls in the hospital setting Design: RCT, CCT, Cohort studies comparing Two cohorts, before	US acute care hospitals Studies: controlled trials and or historical comparison 59 studies	ID through previous reviews & 5 databases, reference list, discussion with content experts IRR, fall rate ratio, pre- post intervention fall rate, and scoring of study details Meta-regression	59 studies met inclusion No statistical significant intervention effects Meta-regression showed no associated connection between levels of intensity on implementation, intervention being difficult to use or compliance Implementation strategies not well documented 91.7%	Limitation: Low no. reported, not enough data to compare fall rates, implemmentation approaches inconsistently documented, intervention multifactor and comparison group did not include that fpi. element, compliance and monitoring compliance were not consistently reported Conclusion: approached to fall

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures & Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
	and after studies, time series Outcome: inpt. Falls, numerical data on interventions, comparison group or data on decreased no. of falls related to the comparator Setting: US acute care hospitals			no doc.) Included staff education, leadership backing, fall committees, quality improvement practices, Interventions: 81% multifactorial, 54% no report on fall	interventions are in existence, but without good documentation of use, compliance, intervention elements and outcomes is needed to prevent falls in the hospital setting DNP project: fall prevention is complex, compliance with assessment tool is important, interventions are multifaceted, difficult to determine which intervention decreased falls

Notes: br = bathroom; cg = controlled group; CRIF = Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research; cct = control clinical trials; cont. = continue; cpg = clinical practice guidelines; cu = control unit; dc = discharge; DV = dependent variable; fpi- fall prevention intervention; FPTK = fall prevention tool kit; fx = fracture; HIT = health information technology; HPPD = hours per patient day; hrs = hours; ic = internal consistency; id = identified; irr = incidence rate ration; iu = intervention unit; IV = independent variable; LOS = length of stay; MFES; modified falls efficacy scale; MRA = Morse Risk Assessment; m.s. = medical surgical; multi-bedded wards = m = bws; NM = nurse manager; No. = number; PAR = Participatory actin research; PI = process improvement; POC = plan of care; Pt.(s) = patient(s); QI: quality improvement project; rct = randomized control trials ; RN: registered nurses; units with single rooms = sr; Stage of Adoption Scale = SAS; StatSoft data analysis software system, version 9.1; Target Risk Factor Fall Prevention Bundle = TRFFPB; Use of Research Findings in Practice Scale = URFPS; V&R = validity and reliability; vs. = versus; yo = years old

Table 2

Nurses' Perceptions

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures, Operational Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
Appraise knowledge, attitude and barriers to encouraging mobility of OA in the hospital setting (Dermody and Kovach 2017)	Qualitative, Descriptive correlation study Variables : Nurses, non-ICU units	Two community-based hospital in US Purposive sample 85 nurses working \geq 20 hrs.	29- question online survey- adapted Overall Provider Barrier Scale Defined: Knowledge barriers to mobility in the OA—lack of understanding the need, skills needed, effects of no mobilization, when to request a PT consult Attitudes barriers—not regarding mobility as important, not expecting mobility to result in positive pt. outcomes, nurse not believing they had the skills to promote mobility Web-based app designed to support data capture for research studies was used, 1 st author did not have access to nurses' info.	Knowledge barrier: 18.% no training to promote safe mobility 56% lack of knowledge in assessment of lower leg strength 84% regarded mobility as important 94% agreed 3XD mobilization improved pt. outcomes 19%- believed mobility was the responsibility of PTs or OTs 19% thought pts. too sick 13% lack of assurance 10% feelings of uncertainty of when pt. mobility was safe	Limitations: limited generalizability, threaten internal validity, mobility type on specified (e.g., up to chair, walking) Conclusion: Knowledge, attitude, and external barriers impact nurses promoting mobility. DNP project: A survey will assist to examine the nurses' knowledge and attitudes on the project unit

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures, Operational Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
Assess the MICU providers knowledge about early mobilization and perceived barriers to provide care (Jolley et al. 2014)	<p>Cross-sectional survey study</p> <p>Also, conducted as part of educational QI</p> <p>Variables: early mobilization knowledge, perceived barriers, RNs, MD, PT</p>	<p>One MICU academic center in Seattle WA 2010-2011</p> <p>Purposive sample</p> <p>120- (17) RNs, (12) PTs, (91) MDs</p>	<p>Two simultaneous cross-sectional surveys</p> <p>Definition of early mobilization: “any activity beyond range of motion performed by a care provider, within 48 hours of mechanical ventilation”</p> <p>Definition of Barriers: “musculoskeletal injuries, fatigue, added work stress, need to stay late in order to catch-up”</p> <p>Followed the Strengthening the Reporting of Observation Studies in epidemiology guidelines</p>	<p>EM Nursing Survey results:</p> <p>13% ROM not enough to sustain muscle strength and EM decrease mechanical ventilation days</p> <p>94% EM possible in pt. on vasopressors</p> <p>18% risk of EM outweighed benefits</p> <p>71% EM placed nurse at risk for injury</p> <p>65% EM added to overall stress</p> <p>47% EM increased work days and delayed other pt. care duties</p>	<p>Limitation: 1 hospital, selection bias, cannot reduced generalizability</p> <p>Authors Conclusion: Most clinicians know EM produces positive pt. outcomes</p> <p>Knowledge, perceived barriers to impeding early mobilization. MDs perceptions.</p> <p>Larger survey-based studies are needed to assess the perceptions and attitudes of nurses.</p> <p>DNP project: Identify barriers on project unit. Include multidisciplinary team</p>
Evaluate nurses’ perception regarding EB fall prevention interventions and efficiency of TRIP intervention to tailor EB fall prevention interventions (conducted at the end of parent study)(Wilson et al. 2016)	<p>Qualitative prospective study</p> <p>Variables: Nurses, EB patient-specific interventions, implementation process</p>	<p>Multi-site, 3 hospitals;13 ms units OH US</p> <p>Acute and sub-acute pts. age 70 to 90 admitted during study period</p> <p>Purposive sample, voluntary</p>	<p>Five 60-90-minute recorded focus group meetings</p> <p>Semi-structured interviews:</p> <p>1. Use of fall prevention interventions before study</p>	<p>Wilson identified 5 major themes</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use of EB fall interventions pt. specific to fall risk factors 2. Beneficial implementation strategies 	<p>Limitations: Nurses only discussed their perceptions of fall prevention interventions on mobility, elimination, and medication. Other categories not discussed. Nurses perception may base on geographic area</p>

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures, Operational Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
		34 RNs who worked \geq 20 hrs., assigned to study unit, provided direct pt. care	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. During study how, their practice was changed to prevent falls 3. Experience with targeted patient-specific fall risk 4. Implementation strategies with targeted patient-specific fall risk 5. Recommendation for future implementation <p>Transcribed by trained transcriptionist, checked for accuracy by trained research assistant. 2 qualitative researchers independently reviewed transcripts. Themes modified as focus groups occurred. 2 researchers ID themes third researcher reviewed. Cross- checking transcripts with audio recording, nurse with implementation of research verified emerging themes</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Overall impact on approach to fall prevention 4. Challenges <p>Discussion of fall prevention targeting mobility- nurses identified getting pts. up, mobile, and strengthening pts. ability to walk as intervention to prevent falls- fall rate decreased 50% Perceptions of challenges: Competing demands, post-fall huddles not helpful,</p>	<p>Conclusion: Nurse perceived pt. specific fall risk intervention and implementation of fall prevention intervention that lessen that risk had a overall impact on changing their fall prevention practice</p> <p>DNP Project: Mobility helps decrease falls. Consider using change champions to implement early mobility practice</p> <p>*Fall Prevention \rightarrow mobility as intervention to address lower limb weakness, unstable gait \rightarrow ambulation 3-4x a day, referral to PT</p>

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures, Operational Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
Assessed the nurses' knowledge and perceptions of the importance of pt. ambulation in the hospital setting (Sepulveda-Pacsi, Soderman and Kertesz 2016)	Qualitative exploratory cross-sectional study	Two urban teaching hospital acute-adult pt. in the US- NY Purposive sample 192 RNS fulltime, part-time, travelers, per diem, work in acute adult inpt. units	Two urban teaching hospital acute-adult pt. in the US- NY Purposive sample 192 RNS fulltime, part-time, travelers, per diem, work in acute adult inpt. units	Knowledge: 90.6% majority of nurse rated themselves as very or fairly. No difference between shifts. 79.3% RNs felt it was their responsibility to ambulate pt. Level of Comfort with body mechanics & ambulating pt.: Only 33% rated very Ambulation 3XD or as ordered: 87.47% rated rarely Nurses perceived short staffing, other pt. emergency, increase in number of pts., and increase acuity as barriers to ambulation, Comfort level, knowledge increased with yrs. of experience	Limitation: All female nurses- limit the generalizability, sample purposive sample from 2 academic teaching hospitals. Conclusion: identifies challenges RNs faced with that prevent ambulating pts.: nurse/pt. ratios, acuity, Further studies to understand obstacles preventing nurses from ambulating pts. DNP Project: 1. Assessing nurses' knowledge, level of comfort, is needed 2. Determine if Missed Nursing Care Survey can be used for project 3. * addresses both perceptions and barriers

Notes: EB = evidence based; EM = early mobility; hrs. = hours; ICU = Intensive Care Unit; id = identify; info = information; MD = Medicine Doctor; nsg = nursing; OA = older adults; OT = Occupational Therapist; pt. = patient; PT = physical therapist; RN = registered nurse; TRIP = translating research into practice; yrs. = years

Table 3

Mobility in Hospitalized Patients

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures, Operational Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
Evaluate the impact of an order set that has a nurse-driven mobility protocol on pts. walking within 72 hours of hospitalization (Drolet et al. 2013)	Quantitative Quasi-experimental design Pre-post implementation Quality improvement project IV: mobility order set with a nurse-driven protocol DV: Daily ambulation within 72 hours of admission	16-bed adult medical/surgical ICU and 26 bed-adult IMCU at a 313-bed acute care community hospital in the US Convenience Sample: pts. age \geq 18 LOS \geq 72 hrs. Pre-implementation: 193 ICU pts. ave. age 67 yo 249 MICU pts. ave. age 65.7 Post-implementation: 426 ICU pts. ave. age 64.4 358 IMCU pts. ave age 68	Chart audits to obtain percentage of patients who ambulated within 72 hours of hospitalization: Pre-3 months and post 6 months	Patients who ambulated within 72 hours of admission: Statistically significant ICU: Pre: 6.2% (12 out of 193) Post: increased to 20.2% (86 out of 426) IMCU Pre: 15.5% (54 out of 349) Post: increased to 71.8% (257 out of 358)	Limitations: completed at only one hospital Conclusion nurse-driven mobility protocol improve patient mobility within 72 hours from time of admission DNP Project: Nurse-driven protocol increases mobility. Complete a literature search for more nurse driven mobility protocols * Barriers- time restraints, believed ambulation was the PTs' job, pt. condition, devices
Investigate if an early standardized process for mobility would decrease PUI in the	Quality improvement project Pre-post-implementation of the	SICU at the University of Michigan Hospital Convenience sample:	Retrospective chart review for risk factors for PUI	Mobility program Post-implementation: 71.3% range 25%-100%	Increase in compliance with early mobility protocol did not decrease PUI

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures, Operational Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
SICU (Dickinson, Tschannen and Shever 2013)	early mobility protocol IV: Mobility Protocol DV: Pt's mobility, PUI	All pts. admitted to SICU between 4 /1/10 to 10/10/10 to the SICU for a total of 1112 pts. (555 pts. pre-implementation mean age 58.2, 557 post-implementation mean age 56.74	Compliance with mobility program Definition of mobility: "a series of planned movements in a sequential manner beginning at the patient's current mobility status with a goal of returning to his/her baseline"	HAPU rate 5.5% pre and 5.7% post no significant difference	Limitation: Pre-implementation mobility data not collected DNP project: This mobility program did not decrease PUI
Evaluate the effectiveness of a dedicated ICU mobility team on four nurse sensitive metrics (Fraser et al. 2015)	Quantitative retrospective longitudinal study IV: ICU Mobility team,	Community acute care hospital in southeastern USA	Retrospective chart review Mobility algorithm Collected data from the hospital's database	Results 66 pts. in SG vs 66 pts. in CG , statistically significant overall P = <0.001 Falls:	Implementation of a mobility team is possible & has a positive impact on nurse sensitive

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures, Operational Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
	mobility team screened pt M-F using the mobility algorithm DV: Pt. mobility, nurse sensitive outcomes; falls, VAP, PUI, CAUTIs, hospital cost	Pts. randomly assigned intervention or control group 3 intervention units: MICU, SICU, & CCU total of 50 beds	Baseline data collected: Random sample prior to early mobility program 66 pts. (8/12 -9/12) SG baseline data gathered 66 pts. (10/12 to 8/13) Definition of Early Mobility: “ the interval starting with initial physiologic stabilization and continuing through the ICU stay”	SG: 0 CG: 2 VAE: SG: 0 CG: 1 PUI: SG: 0 CG: 2 CAUTIs: SG: 1 CG: 12 Hospital cost: SG: 8,270,435 CG: \$8,382,001	outcomes & functional status Limitations: One hospital, intervention only M-F, staff not blinded, changes in intensivist during study, mobility intervention stopped when pt. transferred to medical-surgical unit. DNP Project: This mobility program decreased falls. Might have elements in the program that can be transferable to the medical surgical elderly population
Evaluate the use of a 5-point mobility scale by an early mobility team that included a trained NA as a pt. mobility assistant, skin-care prevention/mobility nurse and PT or OT (Azuh et al. 2016)	Prospective consecutive case series Pilot Study – 1year Quality improvement initiative Pre-& Post pilot staff surveys	MICU @ Henry Ford, Detroit Mich. Convenience sample 3233 MICU admitted pts. at risk for HAPU Braden score < 19	HAPUs, VAP rate, ICU LOS, readmission rate Define Mobility: Level1: BR turn q2h, as needed ROM q4h Level 2: Edge of bed up to 3XD 5-30 min. assisted or active exercise	HAPU rate decreased from 9.2% 6.1% post implementation statistically significant P = .0405 MICU readmission rate decreased from 17.1% to 11.5% post implementation	Use of a mobility team with a trained unlicensed staff member can effectively improve pt. mobility with improved patient outcomes Randomized protocol more powerful than designed used

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures, Operational Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
	Variables: 5-point mobility score Mobility team, plan of care		Level3: Stand to chair: in chair 3XD for 30 min Level 4: chair all meals and walk 3XD with assistance Level 5: Walk independently, in chair all meals, walk 3XD	statistically significant P = .0010 No change in VAP rate Repositioning and help with ADLs increased from 1 st to 4 th qtr. Decrease of 1.2 /1000pts. days	Limitation: Review of data did not confirm if historical control produced population differences, specific infectious epidemics, different referral patterns, socioeconomic circumstances DNP project: explore the feasibility of training a NA to part of a mobility team member as a potential intervention. Evaluate mobility levels for project population.
Evaluate and observe if mobilization during mechanical ventilation decreased ICU acquired weakness (ICUAW) (Hodgson et al. 2015)	Bi-national, Multi-Centre prospective cohort study. Functional status-independent IV: Early Mobilization DV: ICU weakness	12 Adult ICUs Australia & New Zealand 192 pts. age 58.1 ± 58.1	Mobilization during mechanical ventilation, sedation using RASS, ICUAW at ICU d/s, mortality at 90 day and 6-mo, functional recovery Early Mobilization define, "Any activity exercise where the pt. could assist with the activity	Mobilization during mechanical ventilation was no statistically significant difference 50% of pts. d/c from ICU with ICUAW Statistically significant Mortality at 90 days Statistically significant	Early mobilization rare in mechanically ventilated pt. %0% of pt. post ICU admission ICUAW, death associated with ICUAW Total no. of pt. screen not determined. Mobilization not measured beyond 14 days.

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures, Operational Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
			using their own muscle strength and control that occurred while the pt. was receiving invasive ventilation”		DNP Project: Early mobility beneficial however not being done. Reasons why need to be considered when implementing Mobility bundle
Evaluate the feasibility of a mobility protocol(Conradie, Fourie and Hanekom 2017)	A non-randomized experimental pilot	2 x a week all pts. In surgical and respiratory units screened with protocol in the South Africa Convenience sample,138 pts. Age 20- 67 yo	Two positions hemodynamic parameters readings: Map and ScvO ₂ % at 0, 3, and 10 minutes. Definition of Mobility: “Active limb exercise, moving, turning or sitting in bed, on the edge of the bed, out of bed to a chair, standing or walking”	No negative physiologic effect with early mobility MAP no statistical significance Scvo ₂ % remain wnl, no statistical significance	Protocol effective to identify pt. who can tolerate mobility Feasibility of implementing the protocol not fully discovered. The pts. Tolerated mobility interventions. DNP: Early Mobilization is safe. Consideration for barriers such as staff and patients, decrease LOS
An examination of the relationship between ABCDEF (A-F) compliance and pt. outcomes (Barnes-Daly, Phillips and Ely 2017)	A prospective cohort quality improvement Variables: Pt. mechanically ventilated and those	Seven community hospitals w/i California’s Sutter Health System 6064 pts. Medical and Surgical ICUs	Total and partial A-F bundle measured daily and outcomes of hospital survival, coma-free days	Total and partial compliance with A-F statistically significant: Hosp. Survival, delirium free and coma free days	Associated A-F bundle compliance with hospital survival and delirium and coma free days Limitation: no strict protocols, data

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	breathing on their own, ABCDEF bundle	Mean age 63.1			collectors may have had a conflict of interest, unable to determine staffing model on compliance, compliance was with A-F bundle as a whole DNP Project: A-F bundle effective, explore how A-F elements may apply to medical-surgical Units
Evaluate -24-hour OA acutely ill hospitalized pts'. mobility throughout hospital stay. Preadmission OA independently ambulatory and 2 nd purpose-develop and validate a tool to measure mobility level during hospitalization (Pedersen et al. 2013)	Prospective cohort study quantitative Variables: 24-hour mobility measured, pts independently ambulatory at admission,	Copenhagen University Hospital, Denmark 42 OA pts. ≥ 65 yo. Admitted from home with acute illness & at least 1 comorbidity, had capacity to consent and follow directions	Attached two accelerometers to lower limbs, data stored for up to 48 hours Only included LOS > 18 hrs. Algorithm developed to determine pts. mobility, cross validated algorithm Two accelerometers proven to provide valid results in previous studies. Measured pt. walking, pt. sitting, and staying bed in all pts.	Statistically significant were: Amb. Pts. lay in bed (17 hrs.) less than, non-amb. pts. (22 hrs.) Sitting: amb. pts (5.1 hrs.) vs non-amb. (1 hr.) Standing or walking: (1.1 hrs.) vs. (0.2 hrs.) No statistical significance: LOS	Limitation: Conclusion: OA admitted for acute illness spent 17 hours of their hospital day in bed. Increase ambulation was associated with independently being able the time of admission Limitations: unable to determine the difference between standing and walking, not able to measure all pts. throughout hospital stay

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures, Operational Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
Appraise how often and how much time nurse spend with OA promoting mobility in the acute care setting, and who initiates this occurrence (Doherty-King et al. 2014)	<p>Observation study, time-motion Quantitative</p> <p>Variables: RN Staff, OA, mobility activities</p>	<p>Two hospitals Site A: two medical-surgical units at a 81-bed veterans hospital Site B: four units at a academic teaching hospital Midwest US</p> <p>47 OAs pts. admitted to acute care hospital. Pts. mean age of independent: 74.6 yo. Pts. mean age of dependent: 78.9 yo.</p>	<p>Time motion design. Observed nurses as they cared for OA for (standing, walking to and from br. transferring, walking in pt. room and hallway</p> <p>Cite other studies that have used Time motions studies Rigor: describe each researchers role, trained together and agree to definition of mobility</p> <p>Definition of mobility: “standing, transferring, and walking to and from pts. bathroom, and walking in room and hallway”</p>	<p>32% pts. not engage by RN to promote mobility.</p> <p>Mean amb. time: > 2 min/ observation period</p> <p>Standing and transferring mobility activities happened most often</p> <p>Majority of mobility events were requested by the pt.</p> <p>No data to determine if statistical significance</p>	<p>DNP Project: Strengths the need for mobilization of pts. coupled with adverse effects of bed rest for this population</p> <p>Limitation: possible observer error with documenting mobility events, potential Hawthorne effect, mobility could have happened with other disciplines Change in pt. status</p> <p>Conclusion: Nurse do not promote ambulation in OAs, standing and transferring mobility activities happened most often, but because of another task that need to be done for example going to x-ray</p> <p>DNP Project: Nurse spend the most time with the pt. providing an opportunity to</p>

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures, Operational Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
Evaluate the impacted of effective mobility and rehabilitation in the ICU pt. on mortality, functional status, muscle strength, quality of life, ICU and hospital LOS and location pt. was d/c to (Tipping et al. 2017)	Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis IV: active mobility DV: ICU pts.	13 studies were identified from 8380 articles A total of 1753 pts. (880 intervention and 873 control) Adult pt. with LOS > 24 hrs., medical-surgical, trauma pts., from nine different countries, 25 hospitals	PRISMA checklist used for systematic review, Meta-analysis included: RCT and controlled clinical trials Comprehensive search of Authors provide their registration of protocol no. Outcomes were cataloged through the World health Organizational Classification of Functioning, Disable, and Health Define mobility: “active exercise in bed, bed mobility practice, progression of mobility to sitting, to standing and ambulation, tilt table or hoisting to chair” (Tipping et al. 2017)	Mobility and rehab had no impact on the mortality, statistically significant Meta-analysis mobility increased muscle strength @ ICU d/c, improve ambulation activities and more pts. who participated in mobility activities were alive at post d/c days 180. This review and meta-analysis did not show consistent impact on the pts. function, quality of life, ICU or hospital LOS, ventilator days, and discharge location.	promote mobility. Mobility protocol will assist nursing staff in promoting mobility. Limitation: Many articles did not report frequency and duration of mobility activates, small sample size of articles, full impact of mobility is still to be determine Conclusion: mobility of ICU does provide positive pt. outcomes but did not impact days of life. DNP project: Mobility improves muscle strength which can help prevent falls

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Setting & Sample	Measures, Operational Definitions	Results	Authors Conclusion, Limitations; Notes
			Studies screened by two dependent reviewers, resolved by agreement, third reviewer reviewed full text of article deemed acceptable		

Notes: Amb. = ambulatory AVE = average; br = bathroom; CAUTI = catheter associated urinary tract infection; d/c = discharged; CG = control group; HAPUs = hospital acquired pressure ulcers; ICU = intensive care unit; IMCU = intermediate medical care unit; LOS = length of stay; M-F; Monday through Friday; NA = nursing attendant; OT = occupational therapist; Pt.(s) = patient(s); PT = physical therapist; PUI = pressure ulcer injury; qtr. = quarterly; SG = study group; VAP = ventilator associated pneumonia.